
USE OF SOCIAL MEDIA IN LIBRARIES

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Abstract:

This paper covers social media's use in Library it contains mobile based Library, various social services used by the libraries for the benefit of the library users and history of social media.

Key Words: Social media, Libraries, Social Networking, Mobile Services.

Introduction:

Websites offering the users the ability to upload videos, record. Opinions through blogs, wikis, twitter or Facebook and dynamically communicate with individuals have radically changes internet usage. Traditional internet usage was based on static websites, which allowed searching different websites for information and downloading required contents.

Social networking sites and virtual world are at forefront of this development as users are no longer simply engaged with the internet in a passive manner, rather through a huge range of media and through a franche at various inter-faces, including personal computer, mobiles and game consoles.

Social media is just a body to broadcast information quickly-whether the information is good or bad depends upon ultimately upon the individual, how he takes it. Whether he gets lured immediately or waits for the reliable

source and frames his action which may be in favour of whole society.

History of Social Media:

The eighteenth and nineteenth century were leap forward period were gadgets like the broadcast (1972), telephone (1890) and Radio (1891) introduced another time of the sending and accepting messages over long separations. The expending number of express messages between organization, financial and legal offices and banks in developing Urban areas, and also bustling read actively, offered ascend to new strategies for telegram and letter transportation. The twentieth century was set apart by the development and improvement of web, there came period at trade of messages starting with one individual then another next digitally or by means of web.

What Is Social Media?

Social media is hard to define, social media will be defined as any website or software that allows you to

receive and disseminate information interactively.

In the words at Andreas, Kaplan and Michael Haenlein, social media is “a group of internet based applications that build on the ideological and technological foundation and that allow the creation and exchange at user generated content.”

Social Media Means:

Social media is a collective term for websites and application that focus on communication, community based input, interaction, content-sharing and collaboration.

People use social media to stay in touch and internet with friends, family and various communities.

Importance of Social Media:

We can access information in better way. It has been analysed that the people who were not having the access to the internet as a child faced a great deal of difficulty in collecting the information and knowledge required for their educational; purposes with is very easily available to the children of this era.

This impels when you have to do examine on something. You need to spend huge amounts of exertion and 90 miles keeping in mind the end goal to discover books, periodicals, and other paper sources just to begin. Furthermore you may likewise need to lead meets and overviews in order to get more information around specific issues you are handling.

Social networking furnishes interactive involvement with different people groups. Long prior, most kids and teenager were constrained to joining group, neighborhood and social bunches.

Library Services Using Social Media:

- The social media platforms from the independent variables while the library services, librarian provides to their users are the dependent variable.
- The dependent variables are divided into library materials and librarian functions which are books, journals, newspapers, maps, internet bases resources, cd/vcd and lending services, referral services, indexing, abstracting, user education respectively.
- The independent variables are blog, facebook, twitter, whatsApp., youtube, instagram.
- **Blog:** A blog usually provides news or comments on a particular subject or person opinion in text, picture, audio and video format.
- **Facebook:** using facebook can be an effective way for academic libraries to connect with them users community. By posting updates on facebook libraries can inform their users about the library’s programmers and services.
- **Twitter:** Twitter is an effective tool for broadcasting library information, scholarly community appears to be unit in the believe that Twitter should be used by academic libraries to interact with the followers in order to take full advantages of the platform.
- **WhatsApp:** Librarian can easily send free messages to any part of the world without any charge. Librarians can share location, photos, status with their patrons on mobile device. Library need not spend any money for sharing information with their patrons at the tip of their hands.
- **YouTube:** While not officially a search engine after Google the second most number of searches happens on youtube. Their statistics speak for

themselves. YouTube hosts a variety of video content ranging from how-tos, to TV Shows, to commercials, if it's in a video format. You will find it on YouTube creating and sharing your video contents is easy and you have the option of going live too. As a business, YouTube offers you excellent SEO and provides all the analytics you need- all for free more so, you can even advertise on YouTube to increase your reach.

- **Instagram:** Instagram is a free online photo sharing application and social network platform that was acquired by Facebook in 2012. Instagram allows users to edit and upload photos and short videos through a mobile app. Users can add a caption to each of their posts and use hashtags and location-based geotags to index these posts and make them

Searchable by others within the app. Each post by a user appears on their followers' Instagram feeds and can also be viewed by the public when tagged using hash tags or geotags. Users also have the option of making their profile private so that only their followers can view their posts.

Mobile Based Library Services:

- These collections can either be downloaded from the library websites on user-owned mobile devices or libraries lend mobile devices with the collections already on them. A large collection of audiobooks both free and subscription-based services for download and transferable to mobile devices.
- Mobile communication enables libraries to offer location-based content through Global Positioning System (GPS) capabilities.

- Libraries in other countries of the world are successfully providing library services through cell phones.
- The rapid increase on the internet and mobile penetration helping library professionals to keep innovating newer ways at effectively reaching their targeted users and create relevant favorable relationships with them.

Mobile Based Services:

- Opening hours/ Time Saving
- Computer availability
- Catalogue search.
- Location and map.
- User surveys
- Campus directory
- Links to external information providers
- News and event
- Study room reservation.
- Link to campus mobile site.
- Article searching
- Video search / image search
- Quick access to the libraries Facebook and Twitter profiles.

Benefits of Mobile Based Library Services:

- Anytime, anywhere access.
- Increase flexibility for library services.
- Real time data access.
- Instant up-to-date information
- Interaction to user with library professional faculty and colleagues without restriction at time and place.
- Service in the small village.
- Very cheap service.
- Need minimum staff to server.

Conclusion:

- Media Coverage a social media felicitate people with fresh facts and new farming opinions on an ongoing social, political, technical insure and that is why the necessity to insure its liberty is of prime importance.
- In addition, alongside the advantages, students who use social networking tools may pay critical concealed subjective expenses. These sites seize the intellectual development of the users and debase there atoning process and concentration.
- The primary aim of service innovation is to provide the services in such an innovative way so that the users can get maximum satisfaction in terms of time and cost saving.
- Dr. S.R. Ranganathan's five laws of library sciences and his idea i.e., right book / information to the right user at the right in right way is best possible using the new innovative technologies like social networking and mobile apps.
- The social networking in library services and application may bring change in the relationship between user and transform libraries by improving the involvement at users in the services libraries.

Reference:

1. Ahmed, S. (2010). The role of the media during communal Riots in India: A study of the 1984 Sikh Riots and the 2002. Gujarat Riots. *Media Asia*. 37(2) , 103-112.
2. Ballard Barbara (2007). *Designing the mobile user experience*, Hoboken, New Jersey: John wiley & Sons.
3. Fling Brain (2009) *mobile design and development / practical consents technology for creating mobile apps and web site*, Sebastopol, California: oreilly media.
4. Gaikwad, M. N. Use of Social Networking Sites Among Undergraduate Students Of Arts And Commerce College, Madha, Dist. Solapur, Maharashtra.
5. Gupta, Pranav. Abuse of social media. Available on: <http://www.lawctopus.com/academic/abuse-of-social-media.2006>.
6. Social Media: A Journey from facilitator to inflamer by Ahmar Afag and Mohd. Imran. Pg. No. 87-100 pg: *Orient Journal of law and Social Sciences*, Vol. XI, Issue 10th Sep., 2017.
7. Social Networking the “Third Place” and the Evolution of Communication Available at: <https://www.calvin.edu/~dsc8/documents/evolution.atcommunication-NMC-10-07-.pdf>.
8. Prasad, O. Sivasankar. New and innovative services in university library (University of Delhi) New Delhi.
9. Salam, V. & Sing (2007). *Innova line practices in library services: A case study of Manipur University*.
10. Scupola, A & Nicolajsen, H.W. (2010) *Service innovation in academic libraries is there a place for the customers*. *Forthcoming in Library Management*. PP. 304-318.
11. Baruah, Trisha Dowerah. Effectiveness of social media as a tool of communication and its potential for technology enabled connections : A micro-level study (*International Journal of Scientific and Research Publication*, Vol. 2, Issues, May 2012)
12. <http://.invideo.ioablog>.
13. <http://www.techtarget.com>